

The Post Covid-19 Impacts of Tourism on The Host Community: An Empirical Study on Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh

Mizanur Rahman & Burhan Uddin

Abstract

The study intends to identify the influences of the tourism industry on the local people's living standards through economic, socio-cultural, environmental, and health & hygiene during the post-pandemic period. The study is a descriptive research and the data are quantitative in nature. Primary data has been required for this study and it has been considered to collect the data by the questionnaire survey method. A structural questionnaire has been designed and collected data from 370 local people in Cox's Bazar using the five-point Likert scale and convenient sampling. Data were analyzed through SPSS 25.0 using Descriptive analysis, Data reliability test, Correlation analysis, and Regression analysis. The study identified that among the four variables such as economic, sociocultural, environmental, and health and hygiene factors, the economic and health & hygiene variables have positive and significant influences on the host community's living standards. Obviously, the study has certain limitations in consideration of the location and the chosen sample size as both do not represent the country as a whole. This paper contributes to the Governments, NGOs, and tourism industry to make contemporary tourism policies to serve tourists by keeping in mind the host community in this post-covid-19 situation.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a fallout in the world's economy and health system. Since World Health Organization declared COVID-19 as a global epidemic on March 11, 2020, several nations suspended cross-border travel. Many companies stopped operating due to the virus's disruptive effects on the national as well as the global economy. Over 169 million people were infected, with almost 3.5 million deaths worldwide since the beginning of this pandemic. (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022). The global and sectoral economies have encountered crucial damage, among those the travel and hospitality sector is thought to be the most sensitive one. (Hoang et al., 2022). Like many other nations throughout the world, Bangladesh is also experiencing the effects of COVID-19. Bangladesh reported the first COVID-19-positive case on March 8, 2020 (Afreen, 2022). Till October 30, 2022, 2,035,037 cases were confirmed including a death toll of 29,419 and 1,980,148 recoveries (DGHS, 2021). In an effort to limit the virus, physical operations/appearances in all academic institutions as well as all governmental and commercial offices were called to a halt on March 16, 2020. Additionally, mass gatherings were prohibited (WHO, 2020). Entry restrictions were imposed for travelers from nations with a high transmission risk, for example, Iran, Italy, and China (Anadolu 2020). Regardless of these precautions, the statistic report confirmed 145,000 cases and 1,874 losses reaching all 64 of Bangladesh's administrative districts by July 1, 2020. (IEDCR, 2020). The government had to force 'social distancing' rules across the nation to limit the spread. The economy overall and the tourism sector, in particular, have been greatly decimated by this (Sakib, 2020). In Bangladesh, Cox's Bazar is the most traveled destination by domestic and international tourists. Cox's Bazar has the longest unbroken sea beach in the world. On March 24, 2020, the first coronavirus-positive case was detected there. On April 8, the local government declared a lockdown for the whole district to control the spread of the virus (Dhaka Tribune, April 17, 2020). Since the declaration of the red zone, Cox's Bazar has seen a significant decline in the number of both local and foreign visitors. According to Daily star, 250 to 300 million BDT daily transactions dropped while the hotels continue to provide wages and operating costs. According to the tourism authority, in the first period of COVID-19, the travel services and hotel industry lost 9000 jobs where hotel and travel segment contribute 50% and 80% to the loss, respectively because of a sudden drop in international (30%) and domestic (70%) tourists. In particular, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh lost international tourists who travels for their professional purpose in the Rohingya camp in Cox's Bazar. As a result, the average hotel occupancy rate was reduced. Since early March 2020, lots of mid-sized hotels remain closed or are on sale. (The Daily Star, October 31, 2022). According to the tourism-led growth hypothesis, tourism promotes growth in the economy because it generates foreign exchange revenues that are necessary for maintaining international reserves, paying for imports, and buying capital goods. (Narayan et al., 2010; Ehigiamusoe, 2020). In addition to enhancing employment opportunities, technology, and natural resources, tourism also promotes economic growth in agriculture, manufacturing, and construction. The local community benefits since tourism improve the lives of the locals and reduce poverty by creating job vacancies and raising incomes. (Truong et al., 2014; Mbaiwa, 2003; Uslu et al., 2020). As a result, when the global pandemic occurred, it had the most damaging impact on both the tourism sector and people's livelihood, particularly those who were directly involved in the industry. The consequences of the pandemic on the national and international tourism sectors have been the subject of numerous studies. However, their severity on targeted tourist destinations and the host communities is relatively unknown. (Gössling et al., 2020; Ioannides & Gyimóthy, 2020; Haywood, 2020; Sigala, 2020; Romagosa, 2020). The urgency of further empirical investigation into the viewpoints of local residents on the relationship between tourism and COVID-19 is also supported by Sigata (2020). Additionally, several studies which examined the environmental and financial effects of tourism on the community were mostly

carried out at the national and regional levels in numerous tourist attractions (Ehigiamusoe, 2020; Bekhet et al., 2017; Ehigiamusoe & Lean, 2019; Uslu et al., 2020; Mbaiwa, 2003). The study that takes into account how tourism would affect a particular location and the local people in the post-pandemic era is still overdue. This study investigates how tourism has affected the quality of life and economy of local residents in the years following COVID-19 in Cox's Bazar district of Bangladesh. The focus of the current study is to formulate an evidence-based conclusion on the factors and how these factors are influencing the impact of tourism on the host community.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Quality of Life

The phrase "host community" refers to the neighborhood a tourist stays in. Towns or cities that welcome guests and offer them the amenities they require are considered the host community, according to Cook, Yale, and Marqua (2006). The term "host communities" as used by Smith (2001) refers to locals who participate in and/or are impacted by tourism-related activities directly or indirectly because they reside close to a tourist destination. According to Eusébio and Carneiro (2011), quality of life is a multifaceted notion that has become the focus of growing research, particularly in some fields like medicine. Others suggest that life satisfaction is a component of QOL (Eusébio & Carneiro, 2011; Dolnicar et al., 2012), whereas some scholars define Quality of Life in terms of life satisfaction. Dolnicar et al. (2012) state that there is widespread agreement that total perceived QOL is considered a mixture of satisfaction with some life magnitudes. Dolnicar et al. (2012) examined that, regarding the important domains that ought to be taken into account while measuring the construct of QOL, there is, however, little agreement. In the vast bulk of this field's studies, just two categories stood out: material & bett and health. The studies of Andereck & Nyaupane, (2011), Fredline et al., (2012); Meng et al., (2010) have looked at locals' perspectives of how tourism affects their QOL. The majority of studies that have been published in recent years have examined locals' perceptions of how tourism has impacted their towns, rather than their actual QOL.

2.2 Economic Impacts

According to WTTC (2012), tourism influences the local economies in direct, indirect, and induced ways depending on the sector's structure but most importantly on how closely tourism-related activities are connected to the local economy, these can frequently vary significantly between nations. A good range of economic connectivity generally leads to enhancing regional economic activities which further derive to achieve economic growth. The regional economic activities and regional economic growth occurred at the time the tourism industry sources the products and services from the local market or local residents including labor. On the other side, economic activities and growth remained unstable during the dependency on the import of goods and services to eradicate the tourist's needs and demands. The total impacts of this sector are measured as the product of its indirect, induced, and direct effects (WTTC, 2012). The tourism industry contributes to our national and local economy, directly and indirectly, such as trading products and services, creating employment, increasing local people's earnings and income, corporate benefits and profits, tax & vat receipts, and numerous ways. The advocates of tourism describe numerous economic advantages as a driving force behind provincial economic growth and development that boosts homegrown employment prospects, the earnings of foreign currency, and the balance of payments. For the industry to expand and develop, regional tourism promotion is a vital issue (Švajdová, 2018). As Boz (2017) examined and found, tourism is a social, cultural, economic, and environmental spectacle that is important for generating income, providing employment opportunities, and generating foreign exchange (Boz, 2017). In undeveloped and developing nations, it also

contributes significantly to economic growth (Peace et al., 2016). There are numerous studies conducted by the researchers and found and confirmed their findings about the ability of the tourism industry as a driving force for generating incomes, and creation of jobs within local communities that lead to having impacts on both regional and national economies. Finally, it derives towards the sustainable development of local and national communities in a meaningful way (Chiu and Yeh, 2017; Bojanic and Lo, 2016).

2.3 Sociocultural Impacts

As Scholtz, M., (2014) stated that tourism has a wide range of sociocultural impacts that positively influence on host communities. The influences are including improving banking and telecommunication services and infrastructure developments. Though having numerous positive influences on local people there exist some detrimental socio-cultural impacts as well such as western cultural influences i.e., racism & clothing and indigenous language cannibalization. A tourist destination's residents' social behaviors, customs, values, and lifestyles are impacted by tourism, which has an impact on the social culture of that area (Woosnam et al., 2018; Garcia et al., 2015). According to Zaei (2013), the sociocultural effects of tourism can be broken down into different categories, such as regional infrastructure development, facilities development, regional cultural heritage preservation, increasing young exchange programs and activities, increasing events, and minimizing migrants from rural to urban cities. In the Eastern Cape of South Africa, Achiempong (2011) performed research on the relationships between tourism policy and development. The study found that despite numerous beneficial developments in communities' socioeconomic development, there was a lack of cooperation among the government, the local communities, and the private sector. The greatest amount of tourism benefits would be possible if this could be accomplished. Despite having a number of detrimental societal effects, tourism can benefit communities by bringing different cultures together. Visitors and host communities can be benefited from one another by sharing business thoughts, and ideas and grabbing possibilities to promote local communities and entrepreneurs, in addition to learning about various cultural behaviors and values (Zaei, 2013).

2.4 Health and Hygiene:

One of the most important parts of tourism that keep the business alive is health and safety issues at tourist destinations. It has been noted that in the tourism and hospitality industries, COVID-19 and related anxieties put an additional burden on the host community, hoteliers, and food service employees, potentially having a substantial negative impact on their physical and emotional well-being. (Sönmez et. al., 2020). Villacé-Molinero et al., (2021) pointed out that the category for health and safety precautions is quite important in the tourism industry. Clark, C. et al. (2022) Identified six critical drivers of tourism recovery where public health status was shown to be the most significant and unreliable factor of tourist recovery among these six important determinants.

2.5 Environmental impacts

According to Buckley (2009), tourism is observed in numerous forms and categories that have environmental effects in different ways. To protect and preserve the environment, it emphasized on different managerial strategies related to environment preservation (Buckley, 2008). Buckley (2004) conducted a study and found that different types of accommodation such as large-scale resorts and residential programs impact significantly on our environment, especially in rural areas. The detrimental environmental effects lead to soil, air & water pollution (Bearer S., et al., 2008) and disturbance in wildlife habitat, increasing noises, lights, and other types of visual disturbances to host communities (Rolando A., et al.,

2007). Ecosystem affected by sea-based tourism activities lonely which is discovered by GFANC (1997). Ceballos-Lascura' (1996) found direct tourism impacts and classified them into several forms such as impacts on geographical surface, fossils and waters, land, wildlife habitat, vegetation, sanitation, cultural aspects, natural scene, and animals. The summary from the previous studies of Genot (1997) and Wong (2002) successfully proved that about the detrimental and negative effects of tourism on our environment. These include pollution, harm to wildlife & habitat and biodiversity loss, pressure on energy depletion, supply of water, land use, erosion of soil, and pressure on species (Air pollution, Solid waste and litter Untreated wastewater, and Noise pollution). The research demonstrates that locals, who also saw sociocultural advantages, had the most positive perceptions of the economic effects of tourism. Despite their belief that tourism development has a negative impact on the environment, locals support it as a result of this perception. According to Allen & Perdue (1988) tourism has a multifaceted effect on the environment. It might be either favorable or bad. The erosion of cultural or heritage resources, the depletion of natural resources, pollution, and changes in community appearance are some of the detrimental effects of tourism on the host community. They may have an impact on tourism destinations, daily life, and visitors (McCool & Martin, 1994).

2.6 Proposed Research Model

According to Boz (2017), tourism is a social, cultural, economic, and environmental spectacle that is important for generating income, providing employment opportunities, and generating foreign exchange. Despite having a number of detrimental societal effects, tourism can benefit communities by bringing different cultures together. Visitors and host communities can be benefited from one another by sharing business thoughts, and ideas and grabbing possibilities to promote local communities and entrepreneurs, in addition to learning about various cultural behaviors and values (Zaei, 2013).

Figure 01: Conceptual Framework and Research Model

2.7 Hypothesis Development:

Tourism is a social, cultural, economic, and environmental spectacle that is crucial for producing revenue, opening up job possibilities, and earning foreign cash, according to Boz's (2017) investigation and findings (Boz, 2017). The capacity of the tourist sector to be a driving force for producing incomes and the development of employment within local communities that have an influence on both regional and national economies has been established and validated by several studies undertaken by academics. Finally, it contributes to the meaningful sustainable development of local and national communities (Chiu and Yeh, 2017).

H1: There is a positive and significant relationship between Economic impact and the Quality of life of the host community.

Tourism offers a variety of sociocultural effects that have a favorable impact on host communities, according to Scholtz, M. (2014). The factors include infrastructural advancements as well as bettering banking and telecommunications services. Tourism has an influence on the social culture of a location, which in turn has an impact on the social behaviors, customs, values, and lifestyles of its population (Woosnam et al., 2018).

H2: There is a positive and significant relationship between Sociocultural impact and the Quality of life of the host community.

Tourism has a variety of environmental impacts, according to Allen & Perdue (1988). Either a good or poor outcome is possible. Some of the negative consequences of tourism on the host community include pollution, changes in community appearance, and the degradation of cultural or heritage resources, natural resource depletion, and cultural or heritage resource erosion. They could affect tourist locations, daily life, and tourists (McCool & Martin, 1994). A study by Buckley (2004) revealed that various forms of lodging, particularly in rural areas, have a significant negative impact on the environment, especially large resorts and residential programs. Pollution of the land, air, and water is caused by the negative environmental impacts (Bearer S., et al., 2008)

H3: There is a positive and significant relationship between Environmental impact and the Quality of life of the host community.

The importance of health and safety concerns at tourist locations in maintaining the industry's viability cannot be overstated. The host community, hotel owners, and food service workers may experience significant negative effects on their physical and mental wellbeing as a result of COVID-19 and related worries, it has been highlighted. 2020 (Sönmez et al.). The need for safety and health measures in the tourist business is significant, according to Villacé-Molinero et al. (2021). In their identification of the six key factors of tourism recovery, Clark, C. et al. (2022) found that public health status was the most significant and unreliable component.

H4: There is a positive and significant relationship between health and hygiene and the Quality of life of the host community.

3. Methodology

This is a descriptive research and the data are quantitative in nature. Basically, the primary data has been required for this study and it has been considered to collect the data by the questionnaire survey method. A structural questionnaire has been designed. The questionnaire is separated into two different portions. The 1st portion has 5 questions that hold questions related to the demographic profile of the respondents (Gender, Age, Monthly income, Education Level and Occupation. In the 2nd portion, a number of 24 questions have been chosen for the Economic impact, sociocultural impact, environmental impact, Health and Hygiene, and Quality of life of the host community variables. Respondents had to mark and answer 5 questions for Economic impact, 5 questions for sociocultural impact, 5 questions for environmental impact, 4 questions for Health and Hygiene, and 5 questions for Quality of life of the host community. These all questions have been chosen and selected by tourism industry experts, environmentalists, Health care activists, and some other previous excellent research work that are conducted by different scholars in a different time. Conversely, we have used

secondary data also to develop the literature review (Kaushik, 2018; Hasan and Siddique, 2016; Jangra and Kaushik, 2018). The study used the five-point Likert scale in developing a questionnaire for collecting the data where 1 is equivalent to Strongly Disagree, 2 is equivalent to Disagree, 3 is equivalent to Neutral, 4 is equivalent to Agree and 5 is equivalent to Strongly Agree. To minimize the costs and accelerate the research activities we have used the convenient sampling technique, it's one of the nonprobability sampling types (Malhotra, 2008). We have distributed the survey questionnaire among the 370 people who are local residents of Cox's Bazar offshore area one of the most visited tourist places in Bangladesh and collected data accordingly. The questionnaire used the English language only but at the time of difficulty faced by the respondents, we translated the language into Bengali and the Local dialect which facilitated the respondents to understand the survey questions properly in their own tongue and answer the questions appropriately. At the completion of the survey and all the data that are generated from the local people of Cox's Bazar were analyzed through SPSS 25.0 using descriptive analysis, Data reliability test (Cronbach Alpha), Correlation analysis, and Regression analysis (Cronbach, 1951).

4. Analysis and Findings

Table 01: Participants demographic profile

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender of the Participants	Male	227	61.4
	Female	143	38.6
	Total	370	100
Age of the Participants	Below 18	43	11.6
	19-30	204	55.1
	31-40	86	23.2
	41-50	22	5.9
	More than 51	15	4.1
	Total	370	100
Education Level of the Participants	Under Graduate	87	23.5
	Graduate	188	50.8
	Post Graduate	87	23.5
	PhD	8	2.2
	Total	370	100
Monthly Income of the Participants	Below 10000 TK	171	46.2
	10001-5000 TK	127	34.3
	25001-40000 TK	46	12.4
	40001-55000 TK	13	3.5
	More than 55001 TK	13	3.5
	Total	370	100
Occupation of the Participants	Jobless	52	14.1
	Student	188	50.8
	Job Holder	74	20.0
	Self-Employment	56	15.1
	Total	370	100

The table 01 is representing the demographics of the respondents. It demonstrates that the majority of participants (61.4%) are men. and the total number of male respondents is 227 out of 370 respondents where female respondents are almost 38.6% and the total number of female participants is 143 out of 370 respondents. Most of the respondents of this survey are between 19 to 30 years of age which holds 55.1% and 204 in number out of 370 respondents. The age group between 31 to 40 holds the 2nd highest position 23.2% with 86 respondents out of 370 respondents. Under 18 years of age are 43 out of 370 respondents and 3rd highest (11.6%). In terms of percentage, the fourth highest age group (5.9%) included 22 respondents who are between the ages of 41 to 50. Out of 370 responses, those aged 51 and above make up the final 4.1% and 15 respondents. The survey indicates that the education level of most

respondents is graduation (50.8%) 188 in numbers. 2nd highest holds the post-graduate and undergraduate responders about 23.5% and 87 in number out of 370 respondents. 8 Ph.D. holders make up the remaining responses (2.2%). The majority of responders (46.2%) have a monthly salary of less than 10,000 BDT. The second-highest respondents' monthly income (34.3%) ranges from 10,000 to 25,000 BDT. 3rd highest respondents' monthly income was between 25,001 to 40,000 BDT (12.4%). 4th highest respondent's monthly income was 40,001 BDT to up (3.5%). The majority of responders (50.8%) work as students. Job holders make up 20% of respondents, who are in second place. Finally, the remaining respondents (who make up the third-highest percentage of respondents) are jobless (14.1%).

Table 02: Descriptive Analysis

Items	N	Mean
More employment has been created as the development of tourism in Cox's Bazar	370	3.6378
Tourism caused for generating more income for the local people after the post-pandemic period	370	3.1946
Investment opportunities for tourists and businesses have increased.	370	2.9054
The development of the Tourism industry lead to enhance living costs in Cox's Bazar	370	2.9405
Tourism Improved infrastructure development in Cox's Bazar (power, water, transportation, telecommunications, etc.)	370	3.5703
Economic	Avg.	3.2497
The development of tourism provides getting to know different cultures and lifestyles.	370	3.3892
Meetings with travelers have provided the chance to study the customs of other nations.	370	2.9946
The involvement of locals in cultural events has been influenced by tourism.	370	3.3865
My community has seen an increase in tourists, which has resulted in tension and cultural conflicts between locals and visitors.	370	3.8270
The growth of tourism has led to a rise in crime in the city.	370	3.6946
Socio-cultural	Avg.	3.4584
The growth of tourists has caused the natural environment to deteriorate.	370	3.8324
The neighborhood must deal with overcrowding and excessive noise brought on by tourists.	370	4.0081
The city's traffic issues have gotten worse as tourism has grown.	370	3.8189
Development of tourism damages historical structures.	370	3.7865
Tourism development has been responsible for the degradation of natural vegetation /species.	370	4.0405
Environmental	Avg.	3.8973
Tourism development has facilitated the community by getting proper healthcare services.	370	3.3703
The physical health of community members has improved much.	370	3.8054
The host community is happy to have a healthy life.	370	3.6054
The host community has easy access to sanitation and hygiene.	370	3.7865
Health and Hygiene	Avg.	3.6419
The conditions of my life are perfect.	370	3.5946
I can afford a lot of expensive things.	370	3.6892
The improvement of tourism has a good impact on lifestyle.	370	3.7946
I am content with my life in Cox's Bazar as a local.	370	3.4162
The community's citizens now enjoy a higher level of living standard.	370	3.5378
Quality of Life	370	3.6065

The table 02 intended to find out the most significant variables in consideration of having a high mean score. The descriptive analysis exerts that, Environmental (Mean value: 3.8973), Health (Mean value: 3.6419), Quality of Life (Mean value: 3.6065), Socio-cultural (Mean value: 3.4584), and Economic (Mean value: 3.2497) variables are considered as the most impactful factor for this study.

To identify the inner stability of the data we assess the data through Cronbach's Alpha. According to Hair (2010), the data counted as reliable and consistence if the Cronbach's Alpha value is equal to or over 0.70 (70%). The above table described the internal reliability of variables. Five factors we have assessed here and found no internal instability as Cronbach's

Alpha value for the Economic factor is 0.77 (77%), Socio-cultural factor is 0.80 (80%), Environmental factor is 0.76 (76%), Health factor is 0.79 (79%), Quality of life factor is .82 (82%).

Table 03: Reliability of Data

Reliability Statistics		
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Economic	.77	5
Socio-Cultural	.80	5
Environmental	.76	5
Health and Hygiene	.79	4
Quality of Life	.82	5

Therefore, the variables are fit enough and free from consistency error as all the values of Cronbach’s Alpha for all the aspects exceeded to 70%.

Table 04: Model Summary

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.784	.614	.610		.51271

Table 04 estimated the relationship between the factors and exerted the correlation of coefficient among Economic, Environmental, Sociocultural, Health, and Quality of life factors. From the above model summary, we have seen that the R-value is 0.78 (78%) indicating the influential positive and significant affiliation between Economic, Environmental, Sociocultural, health and Quality of life. On the other hand, it expressed the R square value as 0.61 (61%) which indicated the variance between the dependent and independent variables. Adjusted R square is also 61% meaning that the existence of other factors which are not included here might have an influence on tourism impacts on the host community, especially in Cox’s Bazar.

Table 05: Anova

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	152.675	4	38.169	145.198	.0000
	Residual	95.949	365	.263		
	Total	248.624	369			

The aforementioned ANOVA table (table 05) made an effort to highlight the regression analysis of the variables that is carried out by connecting the factor Quality of life with Economic, Socio-cultural, Environmental, and Health. The suggested factors are evaluated in the above table along with the findings. According to this assumption, the F-value is 145.198 and the Sig value is .00 (Sig. $f < .01$). The investigation showed and proved that the model is adequate in terms of fit and stability by achieving 4 and 365 degrees of freedom.

Table 06: Coefficients of the variables

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.597	.159		3.751	.000
	Economic	.305	.047	.305	6.522	.000
	Socio-Cultural	.087	.050	.093	1.742	.082
	Environmental	-.036	.061	-.030	-.602	.548
	Health and Hygiene	.510	.053	.503	9.718	.000

The table 06 examined the link between the factors using multiple regression analysis and discovered that two variables had a positive and significant effect on quality of life of the host community. The economic & Health factor, having a Beta value of .305, a t-value of 6.522, and a P-value of 0.000 and Beta value of 0.503, a t-value of 9.718, and a P-value of 0.00 has a substantial impact on the host community’s quality of life respectively. Thus, H₁ & H₄ both hypotheses are accepted. On the other hand, regression analyses demonstrated that the Socio-cultural and Environmental factors didn’t impact the host community’s quality of life. The values for Sociocultural factors are: Beta = 0.093, t value = 1.742, P value = 0.082 and Environmental factors are: Beta = -0.030, t value = -0.602, and P value = 0.548. Therefore, both H₂ and H₃ hypotheses are rejected.

Table 07: Sum-up of the study

Hypothesis	Variables	Decision
H1	Economic	Accepted
H2	Socio-Cultural	Rejected
H3	Environmental	Rejected
H4	Health and Hygiene	Accepted

Table 08: Correlations among the variables

Correlations		Quality of Life	Economic	Socio-Cultural	Environmental	Health and Hygiene
Quality of Life	Pearson Correlation	1	.665**	.629**	.560**	.735**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Economic	Pearson Correlation	.665**	1	.690**	.557**	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
Socio-Cultural	Pearson Correlation	.629**	.690**	1	.676**	.687**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
Environmental	Pearson Correlation	.560**	.557**	.676**	1	.710**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
Health and Hygiene	Pearson Correlation	.735**	.621**	.687**	.710**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 08 shows all of the significant connections between the components. The 2-tailed Pearson Correlation was used to investigate the associations between the variables, with the correlation being significant at the 0.01 level. As can be seen from the table, all of the independent variables had strong correlations with the dependent variable, with sig f being 0.00. (Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level). Therefore, we may conclude that every element had a major impact on the standard of living in the host community.

4.8. Findings

The study demonstrates that the mainstream of respondents are men and the total number of male respondents is 227 out of 370. Most of the respondent’s age of this survey are between 19 to 30 years of age which holds 55.1% and 204 in number out of 370 respondents. The survey indicates that the education level of most respondents is graduation (50.8%) 188 in numbers. The majority of responders (46.2%) have a monthly salary of less than 10,000 BDT. The study also found the most significant variables in consideration of having a high mean score. The descriptive analysis exerts that, Environmental (Mean: 3.8973), Health (Mean: 3.6419), Quality of Life (Mean: 3.6065), Socio-cultural (Mean: 3.4584), and Economic (Mean: 3.2497) factors are considered as the most impactful factor for this study. According to the association between

the factors using multiple regression analysis and discovered that two variables had a significant influence on the host community's quality of life. The economic and Health factor, having a Beta value of 0.305, a t value of 6.522, and a P value of 0.00 and Beta value of 0.503, a t value of 9.718, and a P value of 0.00 has a substantial impact on the host community's quality of life respectively. Thus, H₁ and H₄ both hypotheses are accepted. On the other hand, regression analyses demonstrated that the Socio-cultural and Environmental factors didn't impact the host community's quality of life. The values for Socio-cultural factors are: Beta = 0.093, t value = 1.742, P value = 0.082 and Environmental factors are: Beta = -0.030, t value = -0.602, and P value = 0.548. Therefore, both H₂ and H₃ hypotheses are rejected. The 2-tailed Pearson Correlation was used to investigate the associations between the variables, with the correlation being significant at the 0.01 level. As can be seen from the table, all of the independent variables had strong correlations with the dependent variable, with sig f being 0.00. (Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level). Thus, all the factors were strongly related to the quality of life in the host community.

5. Limitation, Contribution, Future Research, and Conclusion

5.1 Limitation

Future research needs to address some of this study's shortcomings. The initial impact of tourism on the host community is examined in this study. As a result, independent variables may be modified based on various circumstances. A small sample size is used for the analysis, which is another limitation of this study. The utilization of a large sample size to present wider perspectives from other tourist stakeholders would make the study more intriguing. The study will be more meaningful by increasing the sample size and some other independent variables to gain more useful insight into the tourism impacts on host communities during the post-pandemic period. The study limited by geographical boundaries as it was collected data only from the host community in Cox's Bazar. The study results may have different from the other studies if data will be collected from all the tourist destinations in the world.

5.2 Contribution and Future Research

This paper contributes to making contemporary tourism policies to serve tourists by keeping in mind the host community in this post-covid-19 situation. The COVID-19 pandemic has amply demonstrated the critical need for strategic planning and preparation to lessen its effects. This research also acknowledged the techniques used by people (locals and businesspeople) to get beyond the challenges in this post-COVID-19 situation. For scholars who wish to research about tourism's impacts on host communities, this study will be facilitated them by providing useful data and information. Side by side, the study will be beneficial for the tourism industry to formulate the tourism plan and program by considering the impacts on host communities. Government, and governmental agencies, NGO's and other organizations may use the study to plan and promote their activities in the favor of the tourism industry as well as for the host community obviously.

5.3 Conclusion:

The experiences of locals employed in the tourist industry in Cox's Bazar are examined in this article along with how tourism has impacted both their living standards and the local economy in the period post-COVID-19. It discusses the question of how & what factors are influencing the host community as an influence of the tourism industry in Cox's Bazar area after the pandemic outbreak. To what extent host communities are satisfied with the current (post-covid-19) tourist flow in the area? What steps can be taken to adjust the current situation? The study intended to carry out the most influential aspects of the tourism industry which have impacts on the host community, especially in the Cox's Bazar area. As Cox's Bazar is the most

visited tourist destination in Bangladesh, it's been visited by numerous visitors both local and foreign tourists every year. Therefore, previous studies identified several effects of the tourism industry on the host community or local people of Cox's Bazar. The study recognized the tourism impacts such as economic impacts and health and hygiene impacts on the local people of Cox's Bazar due to the development of the tourism industry as found the same results in previous studies conducted by Villacé-Molinero (2021), Eusébio & Carneiro, (2011), Dolnicar et. al., (2012) and Sönmez et. al., (2020). On the other hand, environmental and sociocultural impacts didn't recognize by the study during the post-pandemic period whereas Buckley (2009) found the environmental impact of the tourism industry on the host community, and Garcia (2015) identified the socio-cultural impact of the tourism industry on the host community.

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